

Real-life data-driven model predictive control for building energy systems comparing different machine learning models

Phillip Stoffel^{*}, Max Berktold, Dirk Müller

RWTH Aachen University, E.ON Energy Research Center, Institute for Energy Efficient Buildings and Indoor Climate, Mathieustrasse 10, 52074 Aachen, Germany

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ABSTRACT

By considering forecasts and exploiting storage effects, model predictive control can achieve significant energy and cost savings in the building sector. However, due to the high individual modeling effort, model predictive control lacks practical applicability. For that reason, data-driven process models, approximating the system behavior based on measurements, have become increasingly popular in recent years. Still, scientific literature lacks consent about the most promising model types and efficient workflows to integrate different machine learning models into a model predictive controller. With this work, we present a workflow to provide efficient model predictive controllers based on measurement data automatically. The main idea is to translate different machine learning models into optimization syntax to enable efficient optimization with full access to gradients. We currently consider artificial neural networks, gaussian process regression, and simple linear regression process models. We use a generic model ontology to automatize the controller generation further and test the methodology on two real-life use cases. The first use case is the application of five office rooms with smart thermostat valves. The second use case is a test hall with an air handling unit and a concrete core activation. Using only two days of initial training data, we deploy controllers based on the different model types for six weeks in the offices and apply online learning to improve the models continuously. We observe only minor differences in controller performance despite the artificial neural networks showing the highest prediction accuracy. The second use case shows that the simple linear models require less controller tuning effort. Thus, for practical applications, we recommend linear regression models.

1. Introduction

We must reduce CO₂ emissions and fossil energy carrier consumption in all sectors to tackle climate change [1]. Particularly heating, ventilation, and air conditioning is an energy-intensive process causing the building sector to account for significant share of the global CO₂ emissions [2,3]. Therefore, enhancing the efficiency of building energy systems (BES) is crucial. An effective measure to do so is model predictive control (MPC). By using a mathematical model of the controlled system and exploiting forecasts for weather and occupancy, MPC achieves significant energy saving potential in buildings. In real-life experiments, Široký et al. [4] report energy savings of 15 to 28%, Drgoňa et al. [5] achieve 53.5% reduction in energy consumption, De Conick and Helsen [6] reduce the energy costs by 34 to 40%, Freund and Schmitz [7] save 30% energy and Sturzenegger et al. [8] 17%. Furthermore, MPC allows considering energy price forecasts and implementing

grid-flexibility services as shown by Cutsem et al. [9], Sawant et al. [10] and Bünning et al. [11]. These flexibility services facilitate the further decarbonization of the electric grid.

However, MPC is still not widely employed in the building sector for several reasons. One of the main reasons is the time-consuming and, therefore, costly controller development caused by a high individual modeling effort [8,12]. A promising approach to mitigate this issue is using data-driven process models. Data-driven process models solely approximate the system dynamics based on measurement data and do not require physical process knowledge. Since those models reduce the modeling effort and are relatively easy to utilize, the so-called data-driven MPC recently gained interest, which reviews by Afram et al. [13], Drgoňa et al. [14], Serale et al. [15], and Kathirgamanathan et al. [16] show. The increasing sensor data availability in the building sector facilitates this development.

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: phillip.stoffel@eonerc.rwth-aachen.de (P. Stoffel), max.berktold@eonerc.rwth-aachen.de (M. Berktold), dmueller@eonerc.rwth-aachen.de (D. Müller).

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Furthermore, data-driven process models can even outperform physics-based models if deterministic process knowledge is unavailable or inaccurate (e.g., natural infiltration and occupant behavior) [17,18].

The scientific literature provides a variety of data-driven process model types used in the building sector. Common model types include multiple linear regression models [19], Gaussian process regression (GPR) [20], and artificial neural networks (ANNs) [21]. However, there is no consensus in the scientific literature regarding the most appropriate model type for broad-scale implementation.

Furthermore, data-driven process models introduce several challenges when used in an MPC. For example, ANNs and GPRs yield in a nonlinear, non-convex optimization problem [21].

Our work contributes to the state of literature by first providing a workflow to automatically translate machine learning models into efficient, gradient-based optimal control problems. Second, we apply ANN-based, GPR-based, and linear regression-based controllers on two real-life use cases to contribute to the discussion of which model type to use for broad-scale application.

In the following, we first discuss the related work to clearly define our contributions. Afterward, we present our methodology, which we subsequently apply to the two use cases in section 3 and section 4.

1.1. Related work on data-driven model predictive control

In scientific literature, various publications demonstrate the high potential of data-driven MPC in different fields of applications. Exemplary applications besides the building sector can be found in chemical engineering [22], engine control [23], control of autonomous (race-) cars [24], quadcopters [25], underwater vehicles [26], and robotic arms [27].

However, especially in BES applications researchers achieve promising results with data-driven MPC. Zhou et al. [28] achieve similar control quality with a regression-based data-driven MPC compared to a physics-based MPC when controlling a simulation model of a university building. Jain et al. [29] control a simulated single zone building using a random forest-based MPC and report only a 3.8% difference in costs compared to a conventional MPC. In an extensive simulation study on a single zone building, Stoffel et al. [30] outperform two physics-based MPCs and a reinforcement learning approach with an ANN-based MPC. Chen et al. [31] control a simulated 16-zone commercial building with ANN-based MPC, outperforming a classical linear MPC by 20%.

As stated above, different data-driven model types can be used for MPC. Among those are linear model architectures like simple multiple linear regression models, which are, for example, used by Wolisz et al. [32] to control the temperature setpoint of a simulated thermal zone. Tabares-Velasco et al. [33] and Lee and Heo [19] control also simulated buildings using linear regression-based MPC. A real-life application using linear regression models is presented by Bünning et al. [34] controlling the radiator valve of a single room. Decision trees or random forests, which also lead to a linear problem formulation, are employed in MPCs for buildings in studies from Bünning et al. [35], Jain et al. [29], and Smarra et al. [36]. Another linear model architecture is a classical state space model derived from linear system excitation. For building control, this model type is for example used by Knudsen et al. [37], Valenzuela et al. [38], and Tariq et al. [39].

Recently, nonlinear model architectures such as ANNs, recurrent neural networks (RNNs), long short-term memories (LSTM), and GPRs have become increasingly popular. However, real-life applications are rare. ANNs as process models for building control are used by Lindelöf et al. [40], Afram et al. [41], Chen et al. [31], Jain et al. [42], and Yang et al. [43]. Mtibaa et al. control a real-life retail building using an LSTM-based MPC in two different studies [44,45].

Studies by Jain et al. [20] and Nghiem and Jones [46] control different simulated commercial buildings with GPR-based MPCs, whereas Maddalena et al. [47] present real-life applications of GPR-based MPCs

in BES. GPRs are often used in stochastic or robust MPC schemes due to the explicit consideration of model uncertainty.

Nonlinear machine learning models like ANNs or GPRs used in an MPC generally yield nonlinear, nonconvex optimization problems. In contrast, linear regression or linear state space models yield linear or quadratic programs allowing the usage of standard algorithms.

Random forests or decision trees can also be reformulated as linear programs as shown by Jain et al. [29], Smarra et al. [48,36], and Bünning et al. [35].

Considering the use of ANNs in an MPC for BES, researchers often employ black-box optimization strategies like exhaustive search as used in different studies by Yang et al. [43,49] to control a real-life office building and a real-life lecture hall. Mtibaa et al. [44,45] use genetic algorithms to set up their LSTM-based MPCs for a retail building. Nunez et al. [50] and Ma et al. [51] rely on particle swarm optimization to obtain the optimal control signals. Other researchers use gradient-based black-box strategies like scipy's *cobyla* [21], and Matlab's *fmincon* [41,52]. Nonetheless, these black-box strategies exhibit computational inefficiency and demand small-scale optimization problems to guarantee real-time feasibility. Consequently, the prediction horizon is commonly short, and a reduced number of control signals are taken into account. This decreases the scalability and effectiveness of data-driven MPC. To overcome this issue, Amos et al. [53], Chen et al. [31], and Bünning et al. [21] use input-convex ANNs.

Yang et al. [54] and Salzmann et al. [55] employ continuous linearization to reduce the computational burden in ANN-based MPC. Others rely on Tensorflow's back-propagation algorithms, providing gradients for more efficient optimization strategies [31,42].

In the case of more time-critical processes like quadcopter [25] and engine control [56,23], these approaches are infeasible. Here, a common approach is translating ANNs trained, for example in Tensorflow [57] into the syntax of specialized optimization tools like CasADi [58] or Acados [59] to efficiently derive gradients and then using efficient numerical solvers like Ipopt [60], and ForcesPro [61].

This approach is also commonly used when employing GPRs as process models in an MPC (also in the building sector) as done in the publications by Jain et al. [20], Nghiem and Jones [46], and Maddalena et al. [47].

To the authors' best knowledge there is no automated workflow in the scientific literature to automatically derive efficient, gradient-based model predictive controllers from machine learning models.

Once employed in an MPC, machine learning models can be retrained continuously with new measurements to increase the model accuracy, adapt to changing environmental conditions, and improve the control quality [30].

However, only few publications consider so-called *online learning* for data-driven MPC. Yang et al. [43] daily retrain an ANN when controlling a lecture hall and an office room for 20 days. The authors show that using online learning continuously increases the prediction accuracy.

Further applications of online learning ANNs in data-driven MPC include the control of quadcopters [25] and chemical processes [62].

When applying online learning for GPRs, the model complexity grows due to an increase in the number of data points. This can lead to real-time and scalability issues as shown by Maddalena et al. [47] controlling a real-life hospital.

Jain et al. [20] mitigate this issue by using the information gain to add only the most informative data points when controlling a simulated office building.

In this context, sparse GPRs are a promising approach for future work [63,64].

Scientific literature provides several real-life applications of data-driven MPC for BES using different model types. However, to the authors' best knowledge, only Bünning et al. [34] evaluate the performance of different model types on the same real-life use case. Bünning et al. [34] apply MPCs based on physics informed MLR, input-convex ANNs, and random forests to control the heating and cooling panels of

two bedrooms. Considering the data requirements and computational effort, the authors conclude that the MLRs are most promising for practical application. In this study, the ANNs performance is weakened due to the input convex structure and usage of black-box optimization schemes.

Our study extends the work of Bünning et al. in various aspects. We additionally consider GPRs and implement all controllers using efficient, gradient-based optimization schemes. Furthermore, we use online learning for all process models and apply all controllers simultaneously to the different office rooms. Thus, each controller’s environmental conditions are the same, allowing a fairer comparison. Lastly, this paper considers two real-life use cases, including a multi-zone problem and a multiple input control problem.

1.2. Contributions

In summary, this paper provides two major contributions. The first is a streamlined workflow to derive model predictive controllers automatically from different machine learning models. The second is the cloud-based implementation and evaluation of GPR, ANN, and MLR-based MPCs in two real-life use cases.

2. Methodology

2.1. Generic formulation of a data-driven model predictive controller for building energy systems

Equation (1a) to Equation (1f) formulate a generic optimal control problem (OCP). In this formulation, we use N to represent the prediction horizon and k for the time steps. The objective function (Equation (1a)) combines the stage costs l_k and the terminal cost l_N . Typically, in the case of BES, the terminal cost l_N is omitted due to stability and convergence not being significant concerns [14]. The stage costs l_k can include multiple terms, often representing an economical cost function based on the costs C_k or energy consumption E_k of the process, both referred to as outputs y_k . Depending on the specific use case, the economic objective is either linearly or quadratically penalized, with the latter providing lower peak loads and enabling demand shaping. To relax the constraints on the state variables x_k (Equation (2)), we introduce slack variables ϵ_k . The penalty on the slack variable is quadratic, allowing significant constraint violations to be penalized more severely than minor ones.

$$\min_{u,x,\epsilon} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} l_k(x_k, y_k, u_k, d_k) + l_N(x_N, y_N, u_N, d_N) \quad (1a)$$

$$s.t. \quad x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k, d_k) \quad (1b)$$

$$0 = g(x_k, u_k, d_k, y_k) \quad (1c)$$

$$0 \leq h(x_k, u_k, d_k, y_k) \quad (1d)$$

$$x_0 = \hat{x}_0 \quad (1e)$$

$$\forall k \in [0, \dots, N - 1] \quad (1f)$$

Every term i of the cost function should be individually weighted with a weight R_i and scaled by the factor n_i to improve the numerical stability.

Moreover, the cost function in this optimization problem typically includes the change of control variables Δu_k , to prevent oscillations in the system. The OCP takes into account both the system dynamics, represented by the dynamic constraint (Equation (1b)), and the algebraic relations through equality constraints (Equation (1c)).

Furthermore, the OCP includes inequality constraints (Equation (1d)). These inequality constraints are used to formulate soft constraints on the state or box constraints for the control variables u_k .

$$x_{\min,k} - \epsilon_k \leq x_k \leq x_{\max,k} + \epsilon_k \quad (2)$$

$$u_{\min} \leq u_k \leq u_{\max} \quad (3)$$

The initial conditions for the state variables are specified by Equation (1e). In data-driven Model Predictive Control (MPC), the approach aims to obtain the necessary process models for the system dynamics (Equation (1b)) based on available data. Typically, these data-driven models are formulated using a (nonlinear) autoregressive structure with exogenous inputs (NARX). Moreover, data-driven models can also capture algebraic relations in Equation (1c). In the following sections, we present an overview of the NARX model structure and the specific types of models considered in this study.

2.1.1. (Nonlinear) autoregressive modeling with exogenous inputs

A NARX model incorporates both present and past values of the inputs and the output itself to describe the system dynamics. The model is represented as follows:

$$x_{k+1} = f(x_k, x_{k-1}, \dots, x_{k-M}, u_k, u_{k-1}, \dots, u_{k-M}, d_k, d_{k-1}, \dots, d_{k-M}) \quad (4)$$

Here, the number of considered previous values, denoted by M , represents the system’s model order or lag. In a NARX structure with multiple inputs, the transfer functions from each input to the output share common dynamics. Thus, considering lags is necessary to accommodate distinct time constants in the inputs [65]. A common lag M is assumed in Equation (4) for presentation purposes.

The example presented above considers one-step prediction, necessitating several consecutive one-step-ahead predictions to forecast multiple steps into the future.

For the function $f(\cdot)$ in the NARX model, this work considers MLR, leading to a linear autoregressive model structure (ARX), ANNs, and GPRs.

2.1.2. Multiple linear regression

MLR is widely used and well-studied in the literature [66,65,67]. In an MLR model, the output y is determined by regression coefficients w_j and inputs u_j , given by:

$$y = w_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p w_j u_j \quad (5)$$

Here, for simplicity, the inputs u_j consider all features of the autoregressive model, including the lags. The regression coefficients w_j are obtained using the least squares approach [66], making training fast and deterministic.

Linear models are well-suited when the system exhibits weak non-linear characteristics. They are particularly useful when dealing with sparse and noisy data and high input dimensionality. In such cases, more informative data might be required to train more complex models [65].

In the context of Model Predictive Control (MPC), linear models offer several advantages. They result in computationally efficient optimization problems and exhibit linear interpolation and extrapolation behavior.

2.1.3. Artificial neural networks

ANNs are a type of parametric learning method within supervised machine learning. In this work, we focus on feed-forward neural networks, also known as multilayer perceptrons.

An important characteristic of ANNs is their ability to approximate any smooth function with arbitrary precision, provided there is sufficient training data [68,69]. This versatility has led to a surge in their popularity in recent years.

In an ANN, each neuron i computes a weighted sum of its input variables $z_{i-1,j}$, scaled by corresponding weights $w_{i-1,j}$, and adds a bias weight b_i . This sum then passes through an activation function $\psi(\cdot)$, which determines the neuron’s output. The output of a neuron i can be expressed as follows:

$$z_i = \psi(b_i + \sum_{j=0}^D w_{i,j} z_{i-1,j}) \quad (6)$$

The activation function used in ANNs is often the logistic sigmoid function [67]. However, other commonly used activation functions include linear functions, ReLU, and softplus functions. An ANN is composed of multiple neurons organized into layers. It typically consists of an input layer containing input variables u_i , an output layer with output variables y_i , and an arbitrary number of hidden layers denoted by L . The output layer usually acts as a simple linear combiner that determines the ANN's scaling and operation point [65]. For the input layer, batch normalization is a popular approach for scaling the input features. It involves normalizing the input features using the mean and variance calculated from the training dataset [70].

$$\hat{u}_i = \frac{u_i - \bar{u}_i}{\sqrt{\sigma_{u_i}}} \quad (7)$$

Batch normalization is known to accelerate convergence and enhance the robustness of the training process [70].

The complexity of the ANN model is primarily determined by the choice of activation functions and the number of hidden layers and neurons per layer. In the context of ANNs, hyperparameter tuning is essential. It involves selecting the appropriate activation function, determining the number of layers, and setting the number of neurons in each layer. When applied in an MPC application, ANNs offer several advantages, including their high approximation capabilities and potential for achieving high accuracy. However, a drawback is that the resulting optimization problem is typically nonlinear and nonconvex. Nonetheless, most activation functions used in ANNs are continuously differentiable, facilitating optimization techniques.

2.1.4. Gaussian process regression

Unlike ANNs, Gaussian Process Regressors (GPRs) follow a non-parametric approach and do not possess a fixed model structure [67]. The output of a GPR is not a deterministic functional relationship between inputs and outputs; instead, it is described as a probability density function. As a result, one of the key features of GPRs is that they not only predict the function values but also provide information about the variance of the predictions. To fully describe a GPR, one needs a mean function $m(u)$ and a covariance function $k(u, u')$:

$$f(u) \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(u), k(u, u')) \quad (8)$$

Here, $k(u, u')$ is commonly referred to as the kernel function, responsible for quantifying the dissimilarity between two data points u and u' .

GPRs are designed to update prior assumptions about the true function based on training data. These prior assumptions consist of the mean function $m(u)$ and the kernel function $k(u, u')$. In many cases, the mean function is set to zero ($m(u) = 0$).

A prominent kernel in GPRs is the radial basis function (RBF), also known as the squared exponential kernel:

$$k(u, u') = \sigma_f^2 \exp\left(-\frac{\|u - u'\|^2}{2l^2}\right) \quad (9)$$

The RBF kernel introduces two hyperparameters in the GPR: the length-scale l and the variance σ_f [71]. The length-scale l serves as an a priori assumption about the smoothness of the function. The variance σ_f^2 controls the variability at points where no training data is available. In addition to the Squared Exponential Kernel, there are several other kernel functions, and their selection and parameterization significantly impact the prediction and variance. Moreover, different kernel functions can be combined by multiplication or addition, yielding another kernel.

The prior in GPRs is determined by the choice of the mean function and the kernel type, without considering the training data. To obtain the posterior, the prior is conditioned with the training data.

For predictions using GPRs, the a priori assumptions are updated using vectorized training data $U = [u_1, \dots, u_O]$ and $Y = [y_1, \dots, y_O]$ with a variance of σ_n^2 for the O observations. The prediction of Y_* based on the test data point U_* follows the posterior distribution of the GPR:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Y \\ Y_* \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} m(U) \\ m(U_*) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} K(U, U) + \sigma_n^2 I & K(U, U_*) \\ K(U_*, U) & K(U_*, U_*) \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (10)$$

The construction of the kernel/covariance matrices, denoted as $K(U, U)$, involves evaluating the kernel function for each data point. Utilizing this probability density function, we can derive the prediction's mean, denoted as $\mu(Y_*)$, and its variance, denoted as $\sigma(Y_*)^2$.

$$\mu(Y_*) = m(U_*) + K(U_*, U)[K(U, U) + \sigma_n^2 I]^{-1}(Y - m(U)) \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma(Y_*)^2 = K(U_*, U_*) - K(U_*, U)[K(U, U) + \sigma_n^2 I]^{-1}K(U, U_*) \quad (12)$$

Hyperparameter tuning for GPRs is as crucial as for ANNs. Typically, to optimize these hyperparameters, the log marginal likelihood is maximized [71].

An inversion of an $O \times O$ matrix is necessary to establish the prediction model, yielding computation costs of $\mathcal{O}(O^3)$. However, this matrix inversion is performed only once. For making predictions, a vector-matrix multiplication (as seen in Equation (11)) is required, resulting in computational costs of $\mathcal{O}(O^2)$. Thus, a major drawback of GPRs is their dependency on the number of training data points when conducting predictions, leading to high computational costs for larger data sets. Despite this limitation, GPRs offer significant advantages in an MPC application, such as generally high approximation capabilities and their implicit consideration of the training data's noise. Moreover, the model uncertainty in GPRs can be leveraged to derive stochastic or robust Model Predictive Control (MPC) schemes. However, similar to ANNs, the resulting OCP becomes nonlinear and nonconvex.

2.2. Cloud-based implementation of data-driven model predictive controller

In this work, we use a self-developed Python framework to automate the implementation of data-driven MPC based on the three model types presented above. The framework is open-source and can be accessed on <https://github.com/RWTH-EBC/DDMPC>.

In Fig. 1, an overview of the core modules of the Python framework developed and the workflow for implementing a controller is presented.

The central concept behind this framework involves converting various machine learning models into symbolic CasADi [58] syntax. CasADi is a tool for algorithmic differentiation that allows us to provide the gradients with respect to the optimization variables efficiently. On the one hand, this facilitates efficient, gradient-based optimization of the resulting nonlinear optimization problem. In this work, we use the interior point solver Ipopt to solve the resulting OCP [60]. On the other hand, the training utilizes specialized tools like *scikit-learn* [72] or *Keras* [73].

Additionally, the framework automatically connects the different inputs of the machine learning models with optimization and parameter variables in the OCP. To achieve this, a generic model ontology is provided, comprising multiple variable types and constructed variables (features). Constructed features are generated by applying mathematical operations to one or more base variables. Additionally, these constructed variables retain information about the applied construction rule in a constraint property.

When implementing a model predictive controller, the user first configures the controlled system. This is done, e.g., by defining the path to a functional-mock-up unit (FMU) or an URL to an HTTP API and then mapping the relevant data points to the model ontology, generating a semantic model. Currently, the framework offers interfaces for FMUs, the BOPTTEST framework [74], and several cloud-platforms. An example for the usage of the FMU interface is given in [30] and for the BOPTTEST interface in [75]. In this work, we use the commercial cloud-

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the developed DDMPC framework.

platform provided by *aedifion*¹ to access the real-life BES. The *aedifion* interface facilitates communication with the *aedifion* cloud platform, granting access to real-time data from buildings and enabling cloud-based control. This interface is developed using the platform's HTTP² and MQTT³ APIs. The HTTP API allows for data exchange through HTTP requests, while the MQTT API supports real-time messaging using the MQTT protocol. These APIs provide the necessary means to interact with the *aedifion* cloud platform and utilize its services for building data retrieval and cloud-based control functionalities. The subsequent step in implementing a controller involves data gathering and processing. The framework offers tools to store, analyze, and process the data. This can entail processing either historical data or conducting system identification experiments. Using the gathered data, the various machine learning models are trained. To achieve this, the framework user specifies the models' structure, such as the number of layers of an ANN considered for hyperparameter optimization, and performs feature selection. Subsequently, the data-driven models are trained and automatically translated into symbolic CasADi syntax.

The OCP is automatically generated from the semantic model and the CasADi process models. At this stage, the user is required to define the objective function and schedules for the controlled variables. These schedules include the lower and upper comfort boundaries for daytime, nighttime, and weekends. Based on the schedules, soft constraints for the controlled variables are automatically added to OCP. Additionally, the box constraints for the control inputs need to be provided.

Once configured, the controller becomes applicable to different systems. During the controller's operation, new data is continuously collected, enabling online learning. Online learning aims to improve the model accuracy and, consequently, the controller's performance by incorporating new information. The framework's major components are implemented as abstract Python classes, allowing easy extension with additional predictors, controlled systems, variable types, and controller types.

In the following section, we give a more detailed description of the process models' generation and the creation of the OCP as the most central part of the workflow.

2.2.1. Generation of process models

During this process step, the user chooses the input features and training parameters for the process models. To maintain modularity, each process model is designed to have only one output. However, when considering multiple states, the output of one process model can serve as input to another process model and vice versa.

To predict future states effectively, the change of a feature is chosen as the output. The change is implemented as a constructed feature. This means that instead of directly predicting the future values of a feature, the models focus on learning the changes in those features over time. By doing so, the following implicit construction rule is added as a constraint to the Optimal Control Problem (OCP):

$$x_{k+1} = x_k + \Delta x_{k+1} \quad (13)$$

The process model subclasses provide varying degrees of freedom when it comes to hyperparameter tuning for different model types. In the case of linear regression models, this process is relatively straightforward since the only degree of freedom is related to the selection of regressors, which is essentially equivalent to feature selection.

Artificial Neural Networks

In the case of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), there are several hyperparameters that can be tuned to optimize the model's performance. These tunable hyperparameters include the number of layers, the number of neurons in each layer, and the activation function used in each neuron.

To determine the best set of hyperparameters, the framework employs a grid-search algorithm as described in [76]. This process involves training various ANNs with hyperparameters varying within predefined ranges. The performance of each ANN is then evaluated on an unseen test set, and the one that performs best is chosen as the final model.

The framework currently considers dense layers, batch-normalizing layers, and different activation functions, such as sigmoid, tanh, ReLU, exponential, soft plus, gaussian, and linear functions.

¹ <https://www.aedifion.com/en/home>.

² <https://docs.aedifion.io/en/developers/http-api/>.

³ <https://docs.aedifion.io/en/developers/mqtt-api/>.

Fig. 2. Five office rooms in a university building are equipped with radiators, smart thermostat valves, and temperature sensors. This allows the testing of different control approaches at the same time.

Certain assumptions are made about the model structure. The input layer always includes batch normalization, and the output neuron is designed as a linear combiner.

While the number of hidden dense layers and their number of neurons can be chosen to have arbitrary complexity, it is recommended to keep them as small as possible to reduce computational burden, of the MPC.

In addition to the architecture-related hyperparameters, the user can also define other training parameters, such as the batch size, the number of epochs, and the choice of the training algorithm (e.g., Adam [77]).

Furthermore, the framework supports the use of early stopping to prevent overfitting during training.

Gaussian Process Regression

When implementing Gaussian Process Regressions (GPRs), certain assumptions about the model structure are also made. In the current implementation, the framework supports only one kernel function, which is a combination of three separate kernels, an RBF kernel, a constant kernel, and a white noise kernel.

$$k(\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}_j) = k_{\text{const}}(\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}_j) \cdot k_{\text{RBF}}(\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}_j) + k_{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}_j) \quad (14a)$$

$$k_{\text{const}}(\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}_j) = c_{i,j} \quad \forall \mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}_j \quad (14b)$$

$$k_{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}_j) = \sigma_i \quad \text{if } \mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{u}_j \quad (14c)$$

In this context, the constant kernel serves to scale the magnitude of the RBF kernel, while the white noise kernel is utilized to estimate the noise level present in the data. This combination of kernels represents a commonly used default choice. The RBF kernel offers distinct advantages for MPC applications, notably due to its infinite differentiability and provision of smooth functions. Nonetheless, the performance of alternative kernels may surpass that of the RBF kernel depending on the specific quantity being approximated. Nevertheless, the framework's modularity ensures that additional kernels can be seamlessly integrated in the future. This flexibility empowers users to explore and incorporate different kernel options to better suit their MPC application and adapt the framework to diverse modeling scenarios.

2.2.2. MPC operation

To finally set up the MPC operation, the user first defines the objective and constraints based on the variables included in the semantic model. Furthermore, the user provides a list of the available predictors. Then the OCP is generated automatically by connecting the semantic model, the construction rules of constructed features, and the prediction rules of the predictors over the given prediction horizon.

Additionally, the user can define a retraining frequency to enable online learning and continuously improve the predictors using newly generated data.

In summary, the presented framework aims at automatizing the development of data-driven MPC. By translating different machine learning models into CasADi syntax, the implementation of the controllers is unified. Thus, a fair evaluation of the different machine learning models' performance in an MPC can be conducted using efficient gradient-based optimization. In the following, we demonstrate the framework's performance on two real-life examples and evaluate the performance of the different machine learning models.

3. Use case 1 - control of five real-life offices

The first use case is the control of five real-life office rooms located on the second floor of a university building in Aachen, Germany. Fig. 2 shows the building together with a floor plan of the considered offices. The building is supplied with heat through a district heating network, utilizing a transfer station. Cooling is not available in the building. The corresponding supply temperature on the building side is determined by a conventional heat curve. The buildings total area amounts to 2104.56 m² with a nominal heating load of 39 W/m². The original setup of individual offices in the building includes Primos radiators with manual thermostat valves. To test the data-driven MPC approaches we retrofitted five offices with battery-powered smart thermostat valves by Shelly.⁴ These new thermostat valves are equipped with Wi-Fi connectivity, enabling them to publish their states every 10 minutes using MQTT. Additionally, the MQTT interface allows users to send control signals to the valves, specifying either the desired temperature setpoint or the valve position. When a temperature setpoint is sent to the thermostat valve, its internal controller, likely a PI(D)-controller, calculates the appropriate valve position to achieve the desired temperature. The internal controller, following a temperature setpoint schedule with night setbacks, provides the benchmark for the data-driven MPC controllers. Instead of controlling the temperature setpoints directly, the data-driven MPC directly regulates the valve position, providing a more advanced and dynamic control strategy. Next to the smart thermostat, we retrofit the considered offices with LoRaWan indoor environmental sensors by enginko,⁵ monitoring air temperature, humidity, pressure, light, volatile organic components, and CO₂.

Fig. 3 shows the communication infrastructure to connect the sensors and the thermostat valves to the cloud-platform. These sensors periodically send their measurements to *The Things Network* (TTN) via a LoRaWan gateway in the building. The measurements are then published to the same MQTT broker used by the thermostat valves for communication. Both the smart thermostat valves and the LoRaWan

⁴ <https://www.shelly.cloud/de/products/product-overview/shelly-trv-1>.

⁵ <https://enginko.com/en/solutions/indoor-environmental-sensor-mcf-lw12co2/>.

Fig. 3. The office rooms' communication infrastructure.

Fig. 4. The office rooms R3 and R4 show a strong thermal coupling. (For interpretation of the colors in the figure(s), the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

sensors are connected to the aedifion cloud-platform. A virtual machine (VM) hosts a parser to translate payloads between the sensors, thermostat valves, and the aedifion format. The aedifion cloud-platform stores time-series data and allows data polling and setpoint adjustments.

The individual offices differ in characteristics. Offices R2 and R4 are unoccupied, making them ideal for comparative controller testing. Offices R1 and R3 are occasionally occupied, each having one user, which slightly influences their behavior. In contrast, office R5 is frequently occupied by up to four individuals, resulting in significant occupant behavior influence. Furthermore, office R5 receives higher solar radiation due to its southeast orientation compared to the other offices.

Additionally, Fig. 2 reveals that offices R3 and R4 are interconnected through a door. Despite being closed, this door facilitates significant heat exchange between the two zones. As a result, the rooms are thermally coupled, meaning that adjusting the position of the thermostat valve in one room directly affects the temperature of the other room and vice versa. The impact of this coupling is clearly indicated in Fig. 4. By opening the thermostat valve in R4, the temperature in R3 rises. Thus, we consider the air temperature of R3 as a feature to predict the air temperature of R4 and vice versa. Then, a combined OCP for both rooms is solved to account for the thermal coupling, yielding a MIMO control problem.

The control task is to maintain thermal comfort and to minimize energy consumption in the considered office rooms. The thermal comfort is represented by temperature boundaries which should not be violated. The temperature limits for all offices are as follows: on weekdays between 9 a.m. and 6 p.m., the lower boundary is set to 20 °C and the upper boundary to 22 °C. Outside of this time frame, we set the lower boundary to 16 °C and the upper boundary to 23 °C.

3.1. Controller design

To achieve the given control task, the violation of the temperature constraints ϵ_k at each time step k is penalized in the MPC's cost function for each office j (Equation (15)). Moreover, the cost function minimizes the valve opening u_{valve} . The latter regulates the mass flow and determines energy usage. Thus, this term introduces an economic objective. Given the absence of energy consumption measurements, a direct penalty on energy consumption is unattainable. A more effective strategy would be to approximate and penalize the flow using the valve's characteristic curve, assuming a consistent supply temperature. Nevertheless, information regarding the valve characteristics of the thermostat valves remains inaccessible. In addition, the objective includes a penalty for changing the valve position (Δu_{valve}) to prevent oscillation and reduce battery drain.

$$\min_{u,x,\epsilon} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left(\epsilon_{j,k}^2 \cdot W_0 + u_{valve,j,k} \cdot W_1 + \Delta u_{valve,j,k}^2 \cdot W_2 \right) \quad (15)$$

When controlling R3 and R4, the objective incorporates the individual terms for both rooms. Therefore, R3 and R4 show how the methodology can easily be applied to multiple coupled zones.

$$\min_{u,x,\epsilon} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left((\epsilon_{R3,k}^2 + \epsilon_{R4,k}^2) \cdot W_0 + (u_{valve,R3,k} + u_{valve,R4,k}) \cdot W_1 + (\Delta u_{valve,R3,k}^2 + \Delta u_{valve,R4,k}^2) \cdot W_2 \right) \quad (16)$$

The weights are assigned equally as $W_0 = 100$, $W_1 = 1$, and $W_2 = 1$ for both Equation (15) and Equation (16). These weights represent the primary goal of a BES, which is maintaining thermal comfort.

Fig. 5. We apply random setpoints to the office rooms over two days (22nd to 23rd January 2023) to generate the necessary training data.

In this use case, we set the prediction horizon to $N = 144$ with a step size of 10 min yielding a one-day prediction.

To account for the system’s dynamics, we need a process model to predict the temperature change $\Delta T_{air,j,k}$ for each office j . In this work, we approximate the temperature change by an ANN, an MLR, or a GPR.

$$\Delta T_{air,j,k} = f_{ann,gpr,lin,j}(\tilde{x}_{j,k}, \tilde{u}_{j,k}, \tilde{d}_k) \quad (17)$$

Due to the NARX formulation, we also consider lagged values of the process models’ inputs. Consequently, the vector \tilde{x}_k incorporates a distinct lag denoted as M^j for each state variable x^j . The construction of the input vector for control signals \tilde{u}_k and the input vector for disturbances \tilde{d}_k follows a comparable approach. In contrast to Equation (4), we assign an individual lag to each input feature to ease the training process and introduce fewer variables to the optimization problem.

$$\tilde{x}_k = \{x_k^1, \dots, x_{k-M^1}^1, \dots, x_k^{dim(x)}, \dots, x_{k-M^{dim(x)}}^{dim(x)}\} \quad (18)$$

For offices R1, R2, and R5, the process models involve the state variable $x_k = T_{air,j,k}$ and the control variable $u_{j,k} = u_{valve,j,k}$.

In the case of the thermally interconnected offices R3 and R4, the state vector comprises $x_k = [T_{air,R3,k}, T_{air,R4,k}]$, while the control vector is $u_k = [u_{valve,R3,k}, u_{valve,R4,k}]$.

The disturbances d_k consist of the ambient temperature T_{amb} and solar radiation $q_{sol,dir}$, which are the same for all offices.

Given the relatively brief duration of application (six weeks) and training periods (two days), factors such as time of day and day of the week are presently excluded as disturbance features.

Hourly weather forecasts and current measurements are sourced from the DWD’s weather service.⁶ Specifically, we use the forecasts from the weather station in Aachen-Orsbach, located approx. 2 km from the building.

Alternatively, we could use the measurements the building’s weather station provides. However, this weather station provides no forecasts. Thus, if we train the models on the historical on-site data, the forecast from the DWD would require adjustment for the different locations. By training on the historical DWD data, we implicitly adjust the model

to consider the location difference. The latter is a further advantage of data-driven MPC compared to physics-based MPC, which relies on accurate on-site measurements and forecasts.

3.2. Identification of the process models

Initially, we generate two days of training data to train the process models. To generate a diverse data set, we apply random temperature setpoints within the comfort boundaries for the internal thermostat controller. Furthermore, we introduce a maximum change from one temperature setpoint to the next to prevent the valves from oscillating between 0 and 100%.

Fig. 5 shows the described excitation experiments. The temperatures are measured by the LoRaWan sensors. In contrast, the thermostats use an internal temperature measurement for control, explaining why the setpoints are not reached. Despite the system excitation, the occupants experienced only minor inconvenience due to the tight temperature constraints chosen for the identification process. We divide the training data into 60% for training, and 40% for testing the GPR and MLR models. In the case of the ANNs, the data is split into 60% for training, 20% for validation, and 20% for testing.

For each model, we select the input features manually. To do so, we perform a correlation analysis and investigate the open-loop performance of the resulting data-driven MPC. Thus, we analyze the controllers’ open-loop prediction to assess if reasonable control decisions are made.

However, for future work, more elaborate feature selection techniques, for example, discussed by Zhao et al. [78] and Rätz et al. [76] should be considered to automate the controller generation fully.

The selected features are presented in Table 1. Note that for offices R3 and R4, the air temperature of the neighboring room with a lag of one is also considered to account for the thermal coupling. In the case of the GPRs, the number of input features should be kept as low as possible. Thus, instead of lags, we use the moving average of the valve position over one hour as an input feature. When training the MLRs, no hyperparameter tuning is necessary. For the GPRs, we use the kernel function as described in subsection 2.2.1. The GPRs’ remaining hyperparameters (length scale, noise, etc.) are optimized using the scikit-learn API [72].

⁶ <https://opendata.dwd.de/weather/1>.

Fig. 6. Experiment 1: Exemplary operation of an ANN-based MPC on office R4. A communication loss causes comfort violations at (I).

Table 1

Features and lags considered to learn the office rooms. Additionally, for the office R3 we consider the air temperature of R4 with a lag of one and vice versa.

MLR		ANN		GPR	
Feature	Lag	Feature	Lag	Feature	Lag
T_{air}	1	T_{air}	1	T_{air}	1
u_{valve}	6	u_{valve}	6	$\bar{u}_{valve,1h}$	1
T_{amb}	3	T_{amb}	2	ΔT_{amb}	1
$\dot{q}_{sol,dir}$	4	$\dot{q}_{sol,dir}$	3	$\dot{q}_{sol,dir}$	1

We use a grid-search hyperparameter optimization strategy for the ANNs. Thus, we train 100 ANNs with varying activation functions, number of neurons, and hidden layers and choose the best-performing network on the test data set for controller implementation. Here, we use Keras [73] and the Adam [77] optimizer. We set the batch size to 50 and train for 400 epochs with early stopping enabled to prevent overfitting.

After the two-day training phase, we deployed the first controllers in the offices for ten days. In this commissioning phase, lasting from January 24th to February 4th, the controllers achieve already promising performance. However, different issues due to implementation errors or network problems occurred in this phase. Therefore, these ten days are unsuitable for a comprehensive controller performance assessment. We provide a more detailed discussion of the commissioning phase, the errors encountered, and mitigation strategies in Appendix A.

Nonetheless, the data generated during the commissioning period is incorporated into the existing training data for the conclusive series of experiments. As a result, we train the final process models for each office on twelve days of data: two days dedicated to the identification and ten days of the commissioning period.

The resulting root-mean-squared errors (RMSE) of the models trained on the twelve-day data set are given in Table 2. The RMSEs are evaluated on the test sets. To continuously improve the process models once in operation, we apply online learning by retraining the models daily with new data.

Table 2

RMSE in K of the process models. The lowest RMSE for each office is colored in green and the highest in red.

	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5
MLR	0.0296	0.0247	0.0299	0.0369	0.0486
GPR	0.0173	0.0162	0.0348	0.0171	0.0315
ANN	0.0279	0.0272	0.0308	0.027	0.0404

Table 3

Conducted experiments in the offices at the beginning of 2023.

Experiment	Period		Office			
	from	to	R1	R2	R3 & R4	R5
Commissioning	24.01	04.02	ANN	GPR	PID	MLR
1	05.02	12.02	PID	MLR	ANN	GPR
2	13.02	20.02	GPR	PID	MLR	ANN
3	21.02	28.02	MLR	ANN	GPR	PID
4	03.03	11.03	ANN	GPR	PID	MLR

3.3. Results of the real-life experiments

We apply each controller type to each office for approx. one week. Therefore, each controller needs to deal with the different characteristics of the different offices. For a fair comparison, we evaluate the overall performance of the controllers by considering their performance in all offices. With the commissioning period, we obtain approx. six weeks of MPC operation for this use case as shown in Table 3. For comparison, we include a baseline PID controller which uses a night setback and a fixed preheating of two hours. In the following, we present one exemplary experiment for each controller based on the different process models. Fig. 6 shows eight days of applying the ANN-based MPC on the thermally coupled office R4. The MPC performs well and consistently maintains the office temperature within comfortable boundaries. By keeping the temperature close to the lower boundary, the MPC minimizes the required heating energy. Only on February 7th a violation of comfort due to a communication loss of four hours is observed.

The MPC's forecasts (depicted in grey) for both air temperature and valve position exhibit remarkable precision. Consequently, the MPC selects the optimal preheating strategy to adhere to comfort criteria at

Fig. 7. Experiment 3: Exemplary operation of a GPR-based MPC on office R3.

Fig. 8. Experiment 4: Exemplary operation of an MLR-based MPC on office R5.

the start of each day. Furthermore, the figure shows that the DWD offers precise predictions for ambient temperature and solar radiation. The GPR-based MPC also effectively ensures thermal comfort while minimizing the activation of the thermostat valve (see Fig. 7). This controller performs well by maintaining thermal comfort and opening the thermostat valve as little as possible, too. The exemplary application of an MLR-based controller for nine days in office R5 is presented in Fig. 8. Compared with the other controllers, the MLR-based controllers do not perform worse.

The prediction accuracy for this office is worse due to the stronger influence of occupancy and the increased solar radiation caused by the southeast orientation. However, we also observe a lower prediction accuracy of the GPR-based and the ANN-based MPCs.

On March 11th, a notable observation is that the process model consistently underestimates heat gains, resulting in lower temperature predictions. Remarkably, this day’s ambient temperature and solar radiation closely resemble those of March 4th, a day less impacted by heat gain effects. The uncertain influence of user interaction with window blinds could impede accurate solar radiation approximation. On March 4th, the users probably adjusted the blinds, which is then considered by online learning. However, due to the weekend, no user interaction with the blinds occurred on March 11th. Thus the blinds are left open, and the effect of solar radiation is higher than before.

In future work, the blind actuation could be integrated into the controller to improve its performance.

Fig. 9. Accuracy of the predicted trajectories considering all offices.

Fig. 10. Average valve opening and discomfort of the different controllers over the average daily ambient temperature. Each mark corresponds to one day of operation of an office. For a fair comparison, the figure contains all experiments on all offices.

In summary, all considered process model types, ANNs, GPRs, and MLRs, provided reasonable and efficient controllers.

To further evaluate the performance of the different approaches, Fig. 9 presents the prediction accuracy of the different process model types over the prediction horizon. This figure considers the deviations of the air temperatures predicted by the MPCs to the measured temperatures for all offices. As expected, the accuracy gets worse over the prediction horizon. Still, the average error remains under 0.5K for the considered 24 h for all model types. This confirms the good performance of the different models. However, the ANNs have the least uncertainty over the prediction horizon, while the GPRs have the lowest average error over the first eight hours.

In general, the models underestimate the offices’ temperatures with increasing prediction horizon. This is caused by two effects. First, the MPC does not have information on the comfort constraint’s rising edge if its more than 24 h in the future. Thus, the MPC predicts a decreasing temperature until it gets information about the edge.

This effect impacts predictions of more than 12 h. For shorter predictions, the main effect is underestimating solar radiation as described above and underestimating internal gains since no features representing these are included. To estimate the overall performance of the different controllers, we evaluate the controllers’ integrated valve opening and discomfort in Table 4. In this context, the valve opening serves as an indicator of energy consumption, which should be as low as possible. Both quantities are aggregated over all offices. The performance of the ANN- and the GPR-based controllers is similar, causing a thermal discomfort of 13.54 and 15.66 Kh, while the integrated valve opening amounts to 267.55 and 275.04, respectively. The MLR-based controller causes slightly less thermal discomfort (10.03 Kh), but has a significantly higher integrated valve opening (325.65). Thus, the data-driven controllers outperform the PID controller by 78 to 86% considering the

Table 4

Optimization time, discomfort in Kh, and integrated valve opening ($\int u_{\text{valve}} dt$) of the controllers.

	MLR	ANN	GPR	PID
discomfort in Kh	10.03	13.54	15.66	71.89
integrated valve opening	325.65	267.55	275.04	343.80
Computation time in s	0.95 ± 0.52	3.06 ± 2.00	11.16 ± 4.66	-

thermal comfort and by 5.3 to 22.2% in terms of valve opening. We must clarify that these numbers do not directly translate into energy savings due to the nonlinear valve characteristics. In Fig. 10, we investigate the discomfort and valve opening, which we averaged daily for all offices and plotted over the average temperature.

Furthermore, regressions over the KPIs for each controller considering all offices are included. Since the PID uses a constant preheating duration independent of the ambient temperature, the PID shows an almost constant valve opening over the ambient temperature. For the same reason, the PID shows higher discomfort for small ambient temperatures.

In contrast, the MPCs preheat longer in case of lower ambient temperatures. Thus, the discomfort is constantly lower than for the PID controller, but the average valve opening is higher for low ambient temperatures (in the case of GPRs and MLRs).

The GPR-based controllers demonstrate the smallest average valve openings across a broad range, whereas the ANN-based controllers lead to slightly higher comfort. The ANN-based MPCs obtain the second lowest average valve opening.

The worse performance of the MLRs is due to the valves’ nonlinear behavior, which the ANNs and GPRs more precisely capture. The characteristics of valves typically follow a sigmoid function, as outlined

Fig. 11. The 630 m² test hall is supplied by an air handling unit and a concrete core activation.

by Kumpel et al. [79]. Therefore, to improve the performance of the MLRs, the sigmoid function of the valve opening could be added as an additional input feature.

Lastly, we evaluate the computational effort for the different model types by analyzing the computation time in Table 4. As expected, the MPCs based on the MLRs need the lowest computation time of approx. one second. In comparison, the ANN-based MPCs require, on average, three seconds, and the GPR-based MPCs eleven seconds. The computation times are low considering the long prediction horizon of 144 and the nonconvex and nonlinear ANNs and GPRs. This confirms an efficient implementation of the control problem.

However, if we consider more complex systems consisting of multiple actuators and control variables, the optimization time is expected to be significantly longer, favoring the use of MLRs.

In summary, these results provide a very fair benchmark between the different model types. However, the outcomes are not universally applicable due to variations in weather conditions despite applying all controllers to all offices.

4. Use case 2 - control of a real-life test Hall

In addition to the office rooms, we applied the data-driven MPC framework to a 630 m² test hall in Aachen. Fig. 11 displays the hall and a schematic of its energy system, which is extensively described by Schraven et al. [80]. The energy system comprises an air handling unit (AHU) and a concrete core activation (CCA) fed by a district heating and cooling network. The AHU supplies air with a desired temperature $T_{ahu,set}$ and a desired humidity. To do so, the AHU has a preheater to prevent freezing, a heat recovery, a heater, a cooler, and a humidifier.

Like the office rooms, the hall is connected to the aedifion cloud platform via a programmable logic controller (PLC). The PLC acts as an edge device and runs the building automation controlling the subsystems. Thus, the data-driven MPCs can also use the aedifion interface to provide supervisory control for the test hall.

In this use case, the desired supply temperature of the AHU $T_{ahu,set} \in [17^\circ\text{C}, 25^\circ\text{C}]$ and the desired flow temperature of the CCA $T_{cca,set} \in [17^\circ\text{C}, 30^\circ\text{C}]$ represent the control variables. Here, we rely on lower-level PID and rule-based controllers, which adjust the corresponding actuators to reach the desired setpoints.

The state variable is the air temperature T_{air} inside the test hall. We approximate the air temperature as the arithmetic mean of the AHU's exhaust air temperature and a measurement of a temperature sensor at 2 m height inside the hall.

The hall is used for scientific experiments causing an irregular usage pattern. Different test benches are placed in the hall, which can lead to significant internal gains of up to 60 kW. This use case is more challenging than the first use case since it has two inputs and combines fast (AHU) and slow dynamics (CCA). Still, the control task is to minimize energy consumption while ensuring thermal comfort. Again, thermal comfort is represented by comfort constraints. Here, we set a

Table 5

Weights R_i of the different OCP configurations.

Controller	R_0	R_1	R_2	R_3	R_4
MLR-MPC	100	1	3	0.5	0.2
ANN-MPC	1111	$\frac{5}{8}$	$\frac{0.5}{13}$	$\frac{2}{8}$	$\frac{0.5}{13}$
GPR-MPC	100	$\frac{1}{8}$	$\frac{1.5}{13}$	$\frac{4}{8}$	$\frac{0.4}{13}$

lower boundary of 19 °C on weekdays between 9 a.m. and 6 p.m. and 17 °C otherwise and upper boundaries of 21 and 22 °C, respectively. The comparatively low temperature of 19 °C is chosen following the energy saving requirements for public buildings in Germany in winter 22/23 due to the gas supply crisis.

4.1. Controller design

We consider the control task in the controllers' cost function in Equation (19). Similar to the first use case, the violation of comfort constraints ϵ_k in each time step is penalized. Furthermore, we penalize the temperature setpoints for the CCA and the AHU. Since we conduct the experiments in the heating season, lower supply temperatures reduce energy consumption (note that cooling with the AHU is deactivated for the experiments). We must change the cost function to save energy in the transitional or cooling period.

$$\min_{u,x,\epsilon} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left(\epsilon_k^2 \cdot R_0 + T_{ahu,set,k} \cdot R_1 + T_{cca,set,k} \cdot R_2 + \Delta T_{ahu,set,k}^2 \cdot R_3 + \Delta T_{cca,set,k}^2 \cdot R_4 \right) \quad (19)$$

Due to the larger thermal inertia of the CCA, we set a prediction horizon of three days with a step size of 15 min ($N = 288$).

As in the first use case, we approximate the ΔT_{air} either by an ANN, a GPR, or an MLR. In the system's state space, we consider T_{air} as the state, $T_{ahu,set}$ and $T_{cca,set}$ as control variables, and the ambient temperature T_{amb} and direct solar radiation $\dot{q}_{sol,dir}$ as disturbances. The DWD provides the latter, like in the first use case. Since the test hall is irregularly used, we do not consider any temporal information as features yet. Compared with the first use case, determining the cost function's weights required more effort. We manually tune the weights based on the MPC's open-loop predictions without applying the control signal. Whereas the first guess of weights for the MLR-based MPC led to reasonable predictions, the GPR- and ANN-based MPCs needed more manual tuning. Especially, the ANN-based MPC reacted more sensitively to weight changes. In this case, a comparatively large weight on R_0 yielded promising open-loop predictions. The resulting weights for the different controllers are summarized in Table 5. We penalize the AHU's temperature for all controllers more than the CCA's flow temperature. Thus, we force the CCA to cover the base load. Additionally, we

Fig. 12. Controlling the test hall's CCA and AHU with MPCs based on different process models.

Table 6
Features and lags used by the different model types.

MLR		ANN		GPR	
Feature	Lag	Feature	Lag	Feature	Lag
T_{air}	1	T_{air}	1	T_{air}	1
$T_{cca,set}$	20	$\bar{T}_{cca,set,2h}$	1	$\bar{T}_{cca,set,2h}$	1
		$\bar{T}_{cca,set,5h}$	1	$\bar{T}_{cca,set,5h}$	1
$T_{ahu,set}$	4	$\bar{T}_{ahu,set,1h}$	1	$\bar{T}_{ahu,set,0.5h}$	1
$\dot{q}_{sol,dir}$	8	$\dot{q}_{sol,dir}$	4	$\dot{q}_{sol,dir}$	1
T_{amb}	8	T_{amb}	4	ΔT_{amb}	1

normalize the weights by the difference of the temperatures' minimum and maximum values for the GPR- and ANN-based MPCs.

Nonetheless, the varying weights indicate that tuning the ANN and GPR-based MPCs is more challenging compared to tuning the linear MLR-MPC. Given the nonlinearity of the models, these MPCs have a tendency to exploit unreliable extrapolation areas and oscillate more. These insights speak for the application of linear MLR models for the widescale implementation of MPC.

4.2. Identification of the process models

We use five months of historical data as a basis to train the different process models. However, during these five months, occasional communication losses, other experiments, and varying operation parameters like varying speeds of the AHU's fans and the CCA's pump occurred. Thus, we filter the historical data regarding these characteristics.

Furthermore, we perform one week of random excitation with the CCA's desired flow temperature.

In summary, we use 24 days of total training data (2304 observations) comprising the excitation experiment and filtered historical data. This data is split into 60% training, and 40% testing data to train the MLR and the GPR and 40% training, 30% validation, and 30% testing for the ANNs. We proceed the same way for hyperparameter optimization and feature selection as in the office rooms. Table 6 presents the features and lags we considered for each model.

For the GPR and the ANN, we consider the moving averages over two hours and five hours of the desired flow temperature $\bar{T}_{cca,set,2h}$ and $\bar{T}_{cca,set,5h}$ as additional input features. A high number of lags is required since the CCA has a high time constant due to its large thermal inertia.

However, GPRs especially struggle with input vectors of high dimension. Thus, we consider the moving average as a feature instead of multiple lags to account for the high thermal inertia.

Considering the AHU, we add the one-hour moving average of the AHU's set temperature $\bar{T}_{ahu,set,1h}$ for the ANN and for the GPR its 30 min moving average $\bar{T}_{ahu,set,0.5h}$.

In this example, selecting features for the MLR model allows using a good guess, whereas more effort is necessary to select the features for the GPR and the ANN manually. However, the performance of one-step-ahead predictions on the test dataset is consistent across all model variants. The MLR model achieves an RMSE of 0.031 K when forecasting air temperature, while the ANN and the GPR yield an identical RMSE of 0.033 K. Considering the short duration of the experiment, we do not consider online learning when applying the controllers.

4.3. Results of the real-life experiments

We conducted several experiments on the test hall with the described controllers in the winter and spring of 2023.

Fig. 12 presents the conducted experiments. In this period, the controllers cause discomfort of 0.02 Kh, (ANN-based), 0.1 Kh (MLR-based), and 0.12 Kh (GPR-based). Thus, all controllers maintain thermal comfort and accomplish the control task. Furthermore, the controllers save energy by keeping the control signals close to the lower constraints mainly and using the CCA more intensively than the AHU. We note that the different MPCs behave similarly. However, the setpoints provided by the ANN-based MPC oscillate stronger.

Furthermore, the MLR-based MPC keeps the hall's air temperature closer to the lower boundary than the ANN- and GPR-based MPCs. This is partly explained by varying ambient temperatures and internal gains. However, the preheating behavior of the CCA varies between the different controllers, too. On February 9th, the ANN-based MPC starts already at 8 pm preheating the CCA for the next day. Therefore, the temperatures barely fall beneath 19 °C, and the controller does not exploit the wider boundaries during the night. Due to the CCA's thermal inertia, the additional heat is released during the day, causing higher daytime temperatures. In comparison with the MLR-based MPC, the GPR-based MPC also exploits the boundaries less. Thus, the ANN- and GPR-based MPCs exhibit minor inaccuracies and are less efficient than the MLR-based

MPC. However, the promising results of the first use case indicate that online learning or prolonged training could improve the results.

The average computational effort of all controllers is low, considering the large prediction horizon of 288 time steps. The MLR-based MPC needs approx. 1 s computing a control signal. With 2 s for the ANN-based MPC and 5 s for the GPR-based MPC, also the nonlinear controllers show reasonable computation times.

In summary, we obtained working MPC controllers based on all considered process model types for this more complex use case. Considering the choice of model type, the simple linear regression models outperform the ANNs and GPRs by showing less effort to train and tune the controller and higher controller performance.

5. Discussion

In total, we applied the MPCs based on GPRs, ANNs, and MLRs for six weeks to the five office rooms and 14 days to the test hall. In summary, all process model types were able to solve the control task by maintaining thermal comfort and showing a reasonable behavior to save energy consumption.

5.1. Choice of data-driven process model type

The accuracy of the different process models is in the same order of magnitude, indicating that the systems are characterized by only weak non-linearities.

Artificial Neural Networks

We deploy relatively small ANNs with one hidden layer and four to 32 neurons to avoid overfitting and reduce computational complexity. However, the ANNs can approximate the systems accurately. In the office use case, the ANNs benefit from continuous online learning. Due to their parametric character, the ANNs can process more training data than the non-parametric GPRs or the simple MLRs.

However, due to their more complex structure, ANNs generally need more training data. This is indicated by the weaker performance in the test hall use case where only little informative training data is available. Still, only two days of initial training data are sufficient in the office use case.

The training of the ANNs is indeterministic and computationally more demanding than the training of the other model types.

Overall, the ANNs are accurate, performant, and recommended if the system is more complex or characterized by stronger non-linearities.

Gaussian Process Regression

We do not observe substantial advantages of the GPRs over the ANNs and MLRs in the implemented configuration. The performance of the GPR-based controllers is similar to the ANNs, but their computational demand is higher.

However, considering the implementation of the GPR-based controllers, several improvements should be evaluated in future work. First, we only rely on one default kernel function. Therefore, future work should improve the kernel selection. One possibility would be an automated kernel selection as proposed in [81].

Furthermore, sparse GPRs should be considered to reduce the computational complexity.

Finally, we do not yet consider the variance of the GPRs. Especially if stochastic or robust MPC schemes are of interest, GPRs can offer an advantage compared to MLRs or ANNs.

Linear Regression

Compared to the GPRs and ANNs, the MLRs are less sensitive toward feature selection and MPC tuning parameters. Thus, the MLR-based MPCs require less effort to set up. We mainly observed this when testing the MPCs in the real-life test hall.

One challenge for applying MPC in buildings is the availability of qualified experts [82]. Therefore, the MPC setup should be as simple as possible, arguing for using MLRs as process models.

Additionally, MLRs have an interpretable model structure, reducing the reluctance of building owners and facility managers toward the algorithm.

The slightly weaker prediction performance of MLRs could be improved by considering non-linear input features like valve characteristics yielding a Hammerstein model structure.

In summary, this work recommends simple linear regression models for practical MPC implementations in thermal zones, confirming the analysis of Bünning et al. [34].

However, for more complex BES or subsystems with stronger non-linearities, ANNs and GPRs might be the better choice. Here, the combination of different process model types could be advantageous. For example, the dynamics of multiple thermal zones could be approximated by linear models, while a non-linear model approximates a central AHU with humidification supplying these zones.

5.2. Comments on the implementation effort

Our main objective when applying data-driven MPC is reducing the overall implementation effort of MPC in buildings. Thus, in this section, we briefly discuss the implementation effort.

We installed the smart thermostat valves in the office rooms on January 8th 2023. Since the first MPC experiments started on January 24th, we needed 16 days to apply an MPC. We needed most of the time to establish a stable internet connection for the valves and write and deploy the parsers to couple the valves with the given cloud platform. Furthermore, those 16 days included the time to understand the valves and how to interact with them, as well as two days of generating the training data.

For the actual implementation of three MPCs based on different process model types, we needed less than one day.

In the ten-day commissioning period, we fixed different, preventable bugs that could be avoided in future applications.

In the case of the test hall, the connection to the cloud platform was already established. However, this application required more system understanding and data preprocessing. Setting up the ANN- and GPR-based MPCs took us one to two days each, mainly due to the feature and weights engineering. In comparison, we only needed one to two hours to set up the MLR-based MPC since the MPC worked reliably with the initial guess for features and MPC parameters.

In summary, we show that the presented framework for data-driven MPC significantly reduces the implementation effort in buildings. Compared with Blum et al. [12] needing 79 days of gray box model development, we reduce the development time to an order of hours or a few days. Furthermore, Blum et al. [12] specify 30 days of controller software development, which is almost not existent in our case due to the modular framework.

The most time-consuming part of our work was the connection of the BES to the cloud platform.

However, commercial companies already provide streamlined workflows to connect building automation systems to cloud platforms.

6. Conclusion

Data-driven models are expected to increase the practical relevance of model predictive control in the building sector and, therefore, increase this sector's energy efficiency and reduce its CO₂ emissions.

Our work provides a streamlined workflow to deploy artificial neural networks, gaussian process regression, and multiple linear regression as process models in a model predictive controller. Here, we apply efficient, gradient-based optimization techniques with full knowledge of

Fig. A.13. Operation of the MPCs in the commissioning period.

the analytical gradients. The workflow's main idea is to translate the different process models into generic CasADi optimization syntax.

Compared to data-driven MPC approaches in scientific literature, which often rely on inefficient black-box optimization techniques, our methodology can efficiently deal with long prediction horizons.

Furthermore, we automated the controller implementation using a generic, variable-based model ontology. Thus, no manual coding is required to set up a controller for a new system.

The modular structure of the framework allows combining the most suitable model type for different subsystems as shown in [83] and easy integrating new features like safe learning as presented in [75]. We successfully apply the workflow to five real-life offices (two are thermally coupled) with smart thermostatic valves and a real-life test hall with an air handling unit and a concrete core activation.

With the presented workflow, we can reduce the MPC implementation effort to a couple of hours or days. However, this requires a fully established connection to the building automation system.

We apply the MPCs based on the different process model types for six weeks in the office rooms, allowing us to compare the models under similar environmental conditions. Here, we use two days of initial training data and then employ online learning to improve the models continuously. In this application, the artificial neural networks yield the highest accuracy. However, we observe only minor differences in performance.

In the test hall use case, the artificial neural networks and the Gaussian process regression model require more effort in selecting the features and tuning the controller.

For these reasons, we recommend the simple linear regression models for practical application.

To fully automatize the controller generation, our future work will consider the automatic creation of semantic system models, automatic feature selection, and automatic tuning of the MPC's cost function.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Phillip Stoffel: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Max Berkold:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Dirk Müller:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Commissioning period

Fig. A.13 shows the first days of operation of the MPCs trained on two days of training data. In general, the controllers achieve already good performance and behave reasonably. However, in this period, some issues occurred. Thus, the commissioning period is not considered for overall evaluation. Nevertheless, the issues provide valuable insights to consider for widescale implementation.

- I On the first day of using the MPCs, occupants requested to increase the comfort limit from 19 °C to 20 °C, which required a restart of the MPC. Dynamic comfort limits should be set to adjust to each office's specific needs based on user feedback to avoid this issue in the future.
- II On the second day of operation, the ERC weather station lost connection to the cloud platform and failed to provide current weather measurements. After that incident, the DWD weather station provides the current measurements.
- III At the 29. January, the server cooling at the ERC failed. Thus, the virtual machines running the MPCs were stopped. In the future, a

commercial provider for server infrastructure should be chosen to provide reliable and scalable service.

- IV The internet connection of the thermostat valves is established using an LTE wifi-router. The contracts with the network provider expired on the 31. January and the thermostat valves lost internet connection. For widescale applications, LoRaWAN thermostat valves should be considered. These valves do not rely on an internet connection, and LoRaWAN has a higher range than wifi.
- V Due to an implementation error, the working memory of the virtual machine was full. The error was fixed for the rest of the experiments.

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